

STRESS MANAGEMENT AND HOME ENVIRONMENT AMONG B.ED STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Everyone experiences stress at some point in their life. We are all familiar with stress-it is a fact of life. With the rapid pace of modern living, it feels increasingly difficult to keep up. The negative effects of stress are widespread and growing. Our stress response is triggered when we are faced with overwhelming demands. The demands can be large or small, but it is the importance we attach to them that decides their impact. Important pressures we feel incapable of coping with result in stress, and prolonged exposure to these reactions can have an impact on physical, emotional and mental health. Most of us feel "stressed out" at least once a month, and the majority of visits to doctors, and days off work, is for stress-related problems. But stress also can grow slowly and go unnoticed, or ignored, for years. Lack of time, information and motivation can cause it to build up until something breaks under the pressure. With this in mind, one of the most important skills we can ever learn is the right way to manage stress. Once the skills are in place, moods become more stable, thoughts become clearer, relationships improve, and the risk of illness diminishes.

Key Words: Stress Management and B.Ed. Students

Need for the Study:

Reducing stress in our everyday life is vital for maintaining our overall health, as it can improve our mood, boost immune function, promote longevity and allow us to be more productive. When we let our stress get the best of us, we put ourselves at risk of developing a range of illnesses – from the common cold to severe heart disease. Stress has such a powerful impact on our well being because it is a natural response that is activated in the brain. Being able to maintain our stress level not only will improve the quality of our work, but also will improve the quality of our life.

In addition to the various physical effects of stress, it can also contribute to a number of mental and emotional disorders, including depression, anxiety, phobias, and panic attacks. This emotional stress can make it difficult to focus, make decisions, think things through or remember things. Stress may also cause irritability, making you easily frustrated and impatient with others, and can even contribute to depression, anger, feelings of insecurity, and relationship conflicts. Many people don't think about stress management unless they're already on the verge of burnout. According to Bosque and Dore (1998), learning and teaching environment ought to implement six functions: inform, communicate, collaborate, produce, scaffold, and manage. They added that conceptually speaking, the learning environment refers to the whole range of components and activities within which learning happens.

Terms and Definitions:

Stress Management - refers to the mental and physical condition that occurs when a person adjust to the environment.

Home environment - refers to all the objects, forces and conditions in the home which influence the pupils physically, intellectually and emotionally.

B.Ed. students - refers to the those who are studying one year B.Ed. programme in various colleges affiliated to Tamil Nadu Teachers' Education University in Madurai district.

Dependent Variable:

- Stress Management
- Home Environment

Independent Variables:

- Sex : Male / Female
- Community : ST&SC / Others

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the stress management of B.Ed. students in Madurai District.
- To find out whether there is a significant difference in stress management of B.Ed. students in Madurai District in terms of select independent variables, viz. Sex, Community.
- To measure the home environment of B.Ed. students in Madurai District.
- To find out whether there is a significant difference in home environment of B.Ed. students in Madurai District in terms of select independent variables, viz. Sex, Community.

- There is a positive relationship between stress management and home environment among B.Ed Students.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The hypotheses formulated for verification in the investigation is as follows:

- Stress Management among B.Ed. students in Madurai district is above average.
- Sex exerts a significant influence on stress management among B.Ed. students.
- Community exerts a significant influence on stress management among B.Ed. students.
- Home environment among B.Ed. students in Madurai district is above average.
- Sex exerts a significant influence on home environment among B.Ed. students.
- Community exerts a significant influence on home environment among B.Ed. students.

There is a positive relationship between stress management and home environment among B.Ed Students.

Methodology-In-Brief:

Sample:

A stratified representative sample of 550 B.Ed. students was constituted from colleges of education in Madurai district with due representation given to the population variables, viz. Sex, Community, Religion, Domicile, Family income, Food habit, College Locality, Residence, Participation in Sports and Games, and Participation in Extra-curricular Activities.

Tools:

The tools used for data collection are as follows:

- Stress Management Scale by Parthiban,S. and Amaladoss Xavier,S.J.(2013).
- Home Environment Scale constructed and standardized by Michael Leo, M. (2009).
- General Information Sheet developed by the investigator.

Statistical Treatment:

‘t’ test for significance of difference between the means of large independent samples was used for analyzing the data.

Saroj Pandey (2004) conducted a study on conflict management Style and stress among school teachers. The findings of the study indicated significant relationship between conflict management style and stress among teachers. The findings indicate certain types of conflict management styles adopted by teachers to reduce stress to considerable extent.

Cinamon; Rachel; Rich, Yisrael; Westman, Mina (2007) conducted a study on "Teacher's occupation - Specific work - Family conflict". This study investigated how work and family generic and occupation - specific stressors and support variables related to family interfering with work interfering with family. The study was conducted among 230 Israeli higher secondary teachers. Results indicated that work - family conflict was related to generic variables and more so to distinctive teaching characteristics.

Stress Management among B.Ed. Students’ in Madurai District:

The average score of stress management among B.Ed. students in Madurai district is found to be 68.31, while the theoretical average is 90 only. This shows that the stress management among B.Ed. students is found to be below the theoretical average level. In other words, B.Ed. students’ stress management is found to be low level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Stress Management and Sex:

The statistical measures and results of test of significant difference between the mean score of stress management among B.Ed. students in terms of sex are presented in Table 1.

Variable	Sub – variables	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Sex	Male	375	71.68	22.39	7.747	S
	Female	175	61.09	9.63		

S-denotes significant at 0.05 level

The calculated ‘t’ value 7.747 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students in the possession of stress management. It is noted that the male B.Ed students’ stress management is better than the female B.Ed. students’ stress management. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Stress Management and Community:

The statistical measures and results of test of significant difference between the mean score of stress management among B.Ed. students in terms of community are presented in Table2.

Variable	Sub – variables	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Community	SC&ST	91	65.31	17.74	-1.721	NS
	Others	459	68.90	20.25		

NS-denotes not significant at 0.05 level

The calculated 't' value -1.721 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between SC&ST and Other B.Ed. students in the possession of stress management. It is noted that the community does not influence on stress management among B.Ed. students. Hence the hypothesis is not accepted.

Home Environment among B.Ed Students' in Madurai District:

The average score of home environment among B.Ed. students in Madurai district is found to be 32.28, while the theoretical average is 26 only. This shows that the home environment among B.Ed. students is found to be below the theoretical average level. In other words, B.Ed. students' home environment is found to be low level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Home Environment and Sex:

The statistical measures and results of test of significant difference between the mean score of home environment among B.Ed. students in terms of sex are presented in Table 3.

Variable	Sub – variables	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Sex	Male	375	36.40	7.135	3.418	S
	Female	175	33.28	6.467		

S-denotes significant at 0.05 level

The calculated 't' value 3.418 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students in the possession of home environment. It is noted that the male B.Ed. students' home environment is better than the female B.Ed. students' home environment. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Home Environment and Community:

The statistical measures and results of test of significant difference between the mean score of home environment among B.Ed. students in terms of community are presented in Table 4.

Variable	Sub – variables	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Community	SC&ST	91	35.96	7.152	0.538	NS
	Others	459	35.30	6.878		

NS-denotes not significant at 0.05 level

The calculated 't' value 0.538 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between SC&ST and Other B.Ed. students in the possession of home environment. It is noted that the community does not influence on home environment among B.Ed. students. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Relationship between Stress Management and Home Environment:

The obtained 'r' value is 0.160, while the critical value is 0.098. Hence there is significant positive relationship between stress management and home environment among B.Ed. students. Hence the hypothesis is not accepted.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions emerged out of the present study are as follows:

- Stress management among B.Ed. students in Madurai district is below the average level.
- B.Ed. students' stress management is independent upon their
 - Community
- B.Ed. students' stress management is dependent upon their
 - Sex
- Home environment among B.Ed. students in Madurai district is below the average level.
- B.Ed. students' Home environment is independent upon their
 - Community
- B.Ed. students' Home environment is dependent upon their
 - Sex

Educational Implications:

Though the stress management of B.Ed. students in Madurai district is low level, this is to be increased to the top level. In this regard, authorities of B.Ed. students should come forward to increase the stress management strategies for B.Ed. students through activities, seminars, debates etc. Many parents may not be aware of the influence of various home environmental factors on the academic achievement of their children. It is recommended that, teachers, educationists and leaders should try to create awareness in parents on the importance of the home environment on academic achievement motivation which can improve the children's performance. The significant difference in stress management among male and female B.Ed. students in very much. The level should be increased to a desirable stage. Hence, apart from curricular activities, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities on stress management techniques enhancement should be organized. The significant difference in stress management among rural college B.Ed. students is much better than the urban

college students. Urban B.Ed. college student's parents should give more importance their ward for developing stress management techniques.

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